

RULE BOOK - ATP -

ALTERNATIVE TRANSIENT PROGRAM

RB-01K.PDF

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I-K. \$INCLUDE Use for Data Modularization

The \$INCLUDE statement is a powerful construction that allows the user to build an EMTP data file by reference to smaller pieces that have been previously established and tested. Each such statement calls for the insertion (or inclusion) of another file at the point of usage. The general form of usage is:

```
$INCLUDE, file_name, arg_1, arg_2, .... arg_N
```

where "\$INCLUDE" must begin in column one, and where all following entries are free-format, separated by commas. Only a single line is presently allowed for the statement (continuation on a second card is not allowed). The first argument is a disk file name indicating where records are stored (more about this immediately below). The second and remaining arguments are optional; they are used only if the disk file being referenced requires them, in which case such arguments must precisely match those of the disk file in number, type, and format. Arguments ("arg_1", etc.) are just character strings without imbedded blanks, although the assumptions and regulations for handling those strings are different for numerical arguments than they are for alphanumeric strings (more about this later). Finally, such \$INCLUDE statements can be nested (imbedded inside of one another) without limit.

Warning! Unless the FORTRAN compiler of the computer being used possesses dynamic OPEN/CLOSE capability, the use of \$INCLUDE is not generally possible. IBM mainframe usage of VS FORTRAN has this problem as last checked during the fall of 1986.

The present section will only treat the usage of \$INCLUDE files that have already been established. That is, there shall be no details about how such files are constructed. Without arguments, the construction is trivial, since any interactive text editor is all that is required. But for arguments, special integer pointers are required, and the creation of these is the work of a separate supporting program (see the servicing of "DATA BASE MODULE" in Section XIX-F).

The first clarification of the initial summary definition of \$INCLUDE usage applies to the first argument, "file name", which is more than just a complete disk file name. More precisely, it is the critical central portion only of a legal disk file name. This root can be augmented automatically by a standard prefix and a standard suffix, which are to be declared as follows:

```
$PREFIX, string_pre  
$SUFFIX, string_suf
```

These two possible declarations are independent of each other in that either one or both can be used. The "\$" must be keyed in column one, as usual. But thereafter, free-format applies, except that the character strings must not involve imbedded blanks. That is, once a string begins, the first blank that is encountered in scanning to the right will terminate the string. There is practically no limit on the lengths of prefixes and suffixes, since strings up to 40 bytes each are allowed for "string_pre" and "string_suf". If no such prefix or suffix declaration has previously been made by the user, then none will be added to "file name" of \$INCLUDE usage, of course. But such automatic augmentation of disk file names is strongly recommended for the serious production user, since it is very powerful, and it allows considerable flexibility at virtually no cost to the user. The addition of a standard file type, version number, directory, disk, and even computer (in the case of networked usage) are all possible — automatically, internally, by the EMTP.

One advantage of using file name prefixes and suffixes is that "file name" can then be made independent of computer (at least for most computers of interest). Consider an example, beginning with VAX-11, which might use the following declarations:

```
$PREFIX, DRB2:[EOGBWSM]
$SUFFIX, .LEC;88
```

Such declarations would precede the \$INCLUDE usage, of course. Then the effect would be that the VAX disk file being referenced by the original \$INCLUDE definition actually be:

```
DRB2:[EOGBWSM]file_name.LEC;88
```

The idea is to make "file name" a character string that will be accepted by all computers of interest (see the "BRIDGE32" example below). The prefix and suffix as illustrated above for VAX-11 are highly dependent on computer, note. Apollo Aegis certainly would not accept such declarations, since square brackets are not used for directories, colons are not used for disks, and version numbers are not preceded by simicolons. But the following would be believable for Apollo Aegis:

```
$PREFIX, //B/WSM/
$SUFFIX, .LEC.88
```

and would result in the total file name:

```
//B/WSM/file_name.LEC.88
```

Note that \$PREFIX and \$SUFFIX will generally appear only once, to define the location of the data base on the computer of interest. Then \$INCLUDE statements will appear over and over, as different components of the data base are requested.

Without arguments, \$INCLUDE usage is trivial. Historically, this is the way \$INCLUDE began: as a \$-card that was processed within the installation-dependent SUBROUTINE CIMAGE. Much as for the FORTRAN construction of the same name (for most computers, if not for the ANSI FORTRAN 77 standard), the result is merely the insertion of a second file in-line at the point of usage. As a simple example involving no arguments and two levels of nesting, see BENCHMARK DC-58 for the computer of interest.

But such simple initial usage was replaced by much more involved usage with arguments, in order to connect to standard, modularized data. Another reason to change was the need to extend from single-phase to multi-phase data input. A paper documenting the change is Ref. 22, Volume 4, No. 2, November, 1983. It is such usage of \$INCLUDE with arguments that dominates the present section. However, whether arguments are used or not, \$INCLUDE has become an exceptional \$-card that no longer is associated with the other \$-cards of Section I-D. Today, \$INCLUDE is serviced by completely different, universal code; it is no longer processed within installation-dependent SUBROUTINE CIMAGE.

It was said before that arguments "arg 1", etc. are just character strings without imbedded blanks. There can be blanks on either side of the comma that separates arguments, but not within the argument itself. If the number of characters in some argument exactly equals the number expected, there will be simple one-for-one substitution in the data field or fields of interest. But suppose the number of input characters does not equal the number expected by the module? Special rules apply to these more complex cases about argument length:

SR1. If the length of any user-specified argument exceeds what the module expects, this is an error, and there will be an error message of which the following is typical (split in 3 pieces for ease of presentation):

```
+++ Argument 2 length-mismatch error. Used on card 5.
    N24, N1 (KBEG), N2 (KEND), N3 (length from $INCLUDE) =
    0  27  32  7
```

For batch-mode usage, correction is not possible, so a KILL = 79 error termination will follow. But for interactive (SPY) usage, the user will be prompted to supply a corrected argument as follows:

```
SEND CORRECTED ARGUMENT (STOP) :
```

Provided the data module is correct, and it is just the reference to it (the \$INCLUDE line) that is incorrect, this provides a powerful extension to former procedures of EMTTP data assembly.

SR2. If the length of any user-specified argument is less than what the module expects, then the argument type must be checked. For a numeric argument, this is acceptable, and the number (the character string which is a number if it is interpreted numerically) is right-adjusted in the data field of usage, with blank fill on the left. On the other hand, if the argument is non-numeric, this is an error, and the result is the same as for the preceding case SR1.

SR3. If the user really wants a non-numeric argument to be shorter than the module expects, this is done by extending the user-supplied name with pounds signs (" "). By definition, this will be converted to a blank at the very end of considerations, after the insertion is complete. Common usage is for node names, for which the module will normally require the maximum of six. Yet users will often shorten this, as would be the case for the 5-character name "PFORM". While pounds signs could in rare cases be imbedded in the middle of a character string, they will usually be placed on either the right or the left edge. For that case, the user must remember which edge, just as with normal node names since the year one.

In order to employ \$INCLUDE as part of his EMTTP data, the prospective user must know what disk files are available, and what the interface requirements are. There is a close analogy between \$INCLUDE usage of the production EMTTP user and libraries of mathematical functions (e.g., matrix inversion, or statistical regression analysis) for the scientific computer programmer. For each proposed usage, there should be an explanation of the purpose of the module, and details of the interface requirements (arguments).

As an introduction to \$INCLUDE usage with arguments, consider the example of Section V of that 1983 Newsletter article, which includes both multi-phase input and data sorting by class. Fig. 1 shows a schematic of the 6-pulse hvdc bridge circuit that is assumed to have been modularized, and at the bottom of the same page 34, there is sample usage that shows the arguments:

```
$INCLUDE, BRIDGE32, ACNOD, MINUS, PLUS, FIRE, MID
```


Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of hvdc bridge circuit. Assumed parameter values are $L_a = 1.E-3$ Henry and $R_a = 3000$ Ohm for the anode reactors and resistors. $R_s = 1200$ Ohm and $C_s = 1.E-7$ Farad for the snubbers.

0) Here BRIDGE32 is the disk file name. If there were previous \$PREFIX or \$\$SUFFIX declarations, then the actual disk file name will be an augmented version of this central root, as explained previously.

1) "ACNOD" is the first argument: a 5-character root name for the 3-phase bus connecting to the bridge. Why only five characters, rather than the more common six? Because BRIDGE32 has been set up so that it will append an "A", "B", or "C" automatically. This illustrates the multi-phase aspect mentioned previously. The user just names the three-phase bus ("ADNOD"), and modularization extends this to the three phases automatically.

2) "MINUS" is the second argument: a self-contained 5-character node name in which right adjustment within the data field of width six is desired. That is, the argument is for an EMTF node name, which normally is six characters. But here the user wanted only five, and has chosen to right-adjust the name, leaving a blank on the left. Note that unlike the first argument, there is no multiphase action associated with the second argument. Although it could have been, the module has not been established this way.

3) " PLUS" is the third argument. It is like the second argument, only with one fewer character. Another single-phase name.

4) " FIRE" is the fourth argument, which provides a multiphase (vector) connection between the grids of the six valves and TACS control system modeling. Although names a 6 characters in length, note carefully that only five have here been provided for: the root word "FIRE" preceded by a blank. This is intentional, and mandatory, since the sixth character is part of the vector extension to the six node names FIRE1, FIRE2, FIRE6. This illustrates that there is nothing inherently 3-phase about multiphase capability. The dimensionality can be arbitrarily chosen by the person defining the module, and is even variable within any one module. Since the six variations are not phases, "vector usage" is probably a more proper term than "multiphase," in this case.

5) " MID" is the fifth argument. It is like the fourth argument, only here there is no TACS connection, and there is one fewer character to the nonblank portion of the name.

Although this example is informative, it fails to show the important exception involving numerical arguments. An example involving numbers was provided in the Newsletter article, which shall be repeated here. See the second argument "45." in both lines:

```
$INCLUDE, DC+, +, 45. , DCPOS , ACTOP
$INCLUDE, DC-, -, 45. , DCNEG , ACBOT
```

Along with the sorting of data by class (Section I-I-J), the processing of \$INCLUDE is all done at the very start of execution, before the EMTP heading is issued. All traces of the origin of the records is lost by the time the EMTP actually reads the records, except for a comment card at the start and a comment card at the end (before possible sorting may reorder records). From BENCHMARK DC-58:

```
C $INCLUDE, DC58INCL1.DAT, --- comment card at the start
  << .... Etc. (omitted cards in middle) >>
C End of $INCLUDE. File name = DC58INCL1.DAT --- end
```

Dimensioning of tables for the \$INCLUDE processing of this section should never pose a problem — provided the program is dimensioned large enough to solve the data case of interest. One cell of List 2 (branch vectors) is required for each argument of any \$INCLUDE card. But these are processed one at a time, so it is only the maximum number of arguments that is limited by List 2 (variable LBRNCH). There is no overflow checking.

I-L. Separate Interactive Plotting Programs: TPLOT and WINDOWPLT

There are two separate interactive plotting programs, "TPLOT" and "WINDOWPLT", that can be used to produce graphs of disk-stored ".PL4" plot files. These are files that were created by previous EMTF simulations having integer miscellaneous data parameter ICAT set to unity (see Section II-B). Although neither plotting program is a part of the EMTF proper, most EMTF users with modern computers will have need of them, so instructions are being placed here in the EMTF Rule Book for convenience of reference.

Interactive plotting means that the user makes his requests for plot variables, scaling, sizes, etc. in real time, while sitting in front of a computer monitor. The computer will rapidly respond with a plot on the CRT screen. If only a character (alphanumeric) monitor is available, the result will be a printer plot. But if a vector-graphic monitor is being used, and if the plotting program supports this, then the result will be a more accurate (and desirable) vector-graphic plot. Since such details are installation-dependent, it is difficult to be more specific in this universal section. See the appropriate installation-dependent subsection of Section I-F for details.

Batch-mode plotting is not considered in the present section, and is a completely separate subject. By definition, batch-mode plotting is that plotting that is a part of an EMTF data case (see Section XIV for details). Of course, any interactive program can be executed in the batch mode, provided the user can anticipate all program prompts for data input, and can key his responses without seeing those prompts. But these are specialized cases that do not modify our fundamental naming distinctions.

"TPLOT" is limited to a single plot on the screen at any one time, whereas "WINDOWPLT" allows several short plots of full width to be stacked vertically on the screen. Although limited to only a single graph at any one time, "TPLOT" is the more general program. "WINDOWPLT" is a special-purpose derivative that lacks many standard features of "TPLOT". But it does allow multiple windows, so it is used only in case the user wants such multiple stacked miniplots. Both interactive plotting programs have hard-copy capability via the "COPY" command, which connects with CalComp plotting software in the batch mode. If the user likes what he sees on the screen following his interactive adjustment, he sends "COPY" to order a paper copy (assuming that the computer of interest has such vector-graphic plotting capability).

The "ERASE" response is associated with blank text of both plotting programs. There are several prompts for labeling that will show an existing (old) label within square brackets. The user can accept this old label (i.e., leave it unchanged) by sending a carriage return (<CR>). But what if the user really wants the text to be blank? Then he sends "ERASE", which can not be confused with a <CR>. The program's response to "ERASE" is the blanking of the character string in question.

The selection among branch variables that are not unique is possible with both interactive plotting programs, whereas no such flexibility is provided by batch-mode plotting. Two or more identical output variable names result from parallel branches of the electric network, of course. If parallel branches have outputs of the same class (branch voltages or branch currents, for plotting purposes), there will be no uniqueness. The plotting program will respond with a warning message that shows all output positions satisfying the pair of user names, followed by an extraordinary prompt for a selection among these. An illustration for the case of 4 candidates follows:

```
Warning! Two or more output variables satisfy the
        user's branch request. Indices of the EMTP
        output vector for these follows, with a "-"
        sign indicating polarity reversal:  5   6  -7  -8
SELECT THE DESIRED ENTRY AMONG THESE:
```

Output positions 5 through 8 all have the same names (NODE2, NODE3) as artificially constructed by the ".PL4" plot file data generator named "PLOTDAT". Examples of the need to select among parallel entries can be found in the test files TPLOT.DAT and WINDOWPLT.DAT that illustrate usage of the two interactive plotting programs.

I-L-1. TPPLOT — for sophisticated, single-window, plotting

When "TPPLOT" is waiting for the user's next command, it issues the prompt ">>> PLOT:". One possible response is "MENU", a command which displays all possible responses. Rearranged to better fit on the printed page, the subsequent output appears as follows:

>>> PLOT :MENU

List of all possible command words follows ...

ALL TIME	AVERAGE	BATCH	CHOICE	COLUMN	CURSOR
EXTREMA	GO	HELP	LABEL	LEVEL	LIMITS
MENU	MESSAGE	MODE	MULTIPLY	NAME	OFFSET
PURGE	REFILE	RESCALE	SET COLU	SET DATA	SIZE
STOP	TIME	TIME UNITS	TIMESPAN	STACK	X-Y PLOT
DEBUG	FILE	LINE	LONGER	PRINTER	PUNCH
SHOW	SMOOTH	BOLD	COLOR	DOT	

The "HELP" command merely results in a display of summary explanations of all possible plot commands. About 130 lines in length, the new user may want to print a paper copy of this file. For most computers, this is just a text file named "TPPLOT.HLP". Explanations that follow will be more conversational: perhaps not complete, but more understandable. The "HELP" file is sort of a dictionary of short explanations.

"FILE" is the first request of most users as execution begins. It will result in a prompt for the name of a disk file of raw plot data points. Since file names are computer-dependent, it is impossible to be specific. The six digits of the time at the beginning of execution (HH.MM.SS) will usually be involved. So should the six digits of the date, if the computer permits such longer names. As to whether a missing root name (e.g., "PLOT" of Apollo), date (DD-Mth-YY), or file type (".PL4" for most systems) is supplied automatically, see computer-specific details in Section I-F. In all cases, a response beginning with a percent sign ("%") is taken as the indication that a complete, legal, file name follows. Any example that requests the standard test file produced by "PLOTDAT" follows:

>>> PLOT :FILE

SUPPLY DISK FILE NAME (HHMMSS):%HHMMSS.PL4

Should another file be connected when this request is received, that other plot file will be released automatically before the new file is connected, of course. Hence the "FILE" request can be used as often as is desired.

"CHOICE" is the request for a tabulation of available EMTF output variables. It can only be used after "FILE" (i.e., after a plot file has been connected).

"NAME" provides the initiation of variable specification for the next plot. There are three classes of variables for plot purposes: 1) node voltages; 2) branch voltages; 3) branch currents. Variable specification is sequential, with one class continuing until "END" switches to the following class, in the order stated. After the last variable of interest, "LAST" will terminate the variable specification and return to the ">>> PLOT:" prompt. As an example, consider the specification of one node voltage and one branch current (see top of next page):

```

>>> PLOT :NAME
      SEND NODE NAME OR END [      ] :NODE1
      SEND NODE NAME OR END [      ] :END
      SEND BRANCH VOLTAGE NAMES OR END [NODE2 ,      ] :END
      SEND BRANCH CURRENT NAMES OR END [NODE2 ,      ] :NODE2 NODE3
      SEND BRANCH CURRENT NAMES OR END [      ,      ] :LAST

```

"MODE" toggles the switch that chooses between character plotting and vector-graphic plotting. The default setting will depend on computer (consult Section I-F).

"LABEL" begins the specification of plot labels (super title, vertical axis label, and the multi-line case title). To reuse a previous label (shown within square brackets), send just <CR>. For the case title, "FLUSH" will rewind the pointer that counts lines. The text will remain, to be accepted or rejected line by line. To show the entire case title, "PLAYBACK" can be used at any point before the terminating "END" freezes it. If no labels are ever specified, they will be blank, by default.

"TIMESPAN" will result in the experimental determination of beginning and ending times of the plot data. After such usage, units will be in [sec], and "ALL TIME" can be used for a complete plot of all time instants of the chose curves. An example follows:

```

>>> PLOT :TIMESPAN
      11 Time points. T-min, T-max [sec] = 0.00000E+00 6.28319E+00

```

"ALL TIME" is the request for a plot over the full time range of available data. This only works if the "TIMESPAN" command previously has been issued.

"TIME UNITS" is used to specify the desired units of time for all such quantities. Just as with batch-mode plotting of Section XIV, integer codes are used to respond to a following prompt:

- 1 ==> Degrees based on the power frequency;
- 2 ==> Cycles based on the power frequency;
- 3 ==> Seconds;
- 4 ==> Milliseconds
- 5 ==> Microseconds
- 6 ==> Hertz (for usage with "FREQUENCY SCAN");
- 7 ==> Log to the base 10 of Hertz.

"TIME" is the request to input time-axis limits T-min and T-max of the plot in response to a subsequent prompt. This serves as the command to perform the plot, too. An alternate command to perform the plot is "GO", which will reuse the preceding T-min and T-max.

"LIMITS" is the request for manual specification of the vertical axis limits. There will be a subsequent prompt for the axis minimum and maximum, and this will include the current limits within square brackets. As an illustration:

```

      VERTICAL MIN & MAX [ -2.000E+01 2.000E+01 ] :

```

Send a pair of zeros to cancel such previous usage and return to automatic, internal scaling of the vertical axis.

"FACTOR" and "OFFSET" are requests for multiplicative and additive modifications to all ordinates of all curve. These are the variables "A" and "B", respectively, of the linear mapping $z = A * y + B$. Each command will require the input of a vector of free-format values --- one "A" and/or "B" for each curve being plotted. Of course, the initial, default setting has "A" equal to unity and "B" equal to zero. Other values are common in cases where variables of different types (e.g., one shaft torque and one armature current of a synchronous machine) are to be plotted on the same graph. To return to natural (default) scaling after such use, the user can send "RESCALE".

"SET DATA" is used to override default parameter values with user preferences that have been pre-stored in a disk file having the reserved named TPPARAM.DAT (for most computers). The program response to a "SET DATA" command will be a prompt showing four alternative responses:

Select (MENU LIST END SELECT) :

"MENU" will result in a display of all comment cards contained in each data subset in turn. As long as the user summarizes the purpose of each data subset on comment cards, this provides a handy online summary of available alternatives. Even without any comment cards, it shows the user which subset numbers are legal. If the user wants to see a listing of the entire contents of the file, he can type "LIST". This generally would be used only by those not having windows, since with windows, it is easier just to edit the file. To exit considerations of "SET DATA" and return to the ">>> PLOT:" prompt, send "END". Finally, to specify a subset of plot parameters to be loaded, send "SELECT", followed by the appropriate subset number after a subsequent prompt for it. But what if available data subsets do not provide all that the user wants? In this case, the user can add his own data subset to the end of the TPPARAM.DAT file. There can be an arbitrary number of such subsets, with each having three classes of variables: REAL (floating-point), INTEGERS, and A8 alphanumeric command words, in that order. Each parameter change requires one line of the file, and this consists of two values: first the index number, and second the desired parameter value. But which parameter should be changed? The following list of common numerical parameters should satisfy most needs. First come the REALs, then the INTEGER variables, corresponding to the required order within disk file TPPARAM.DAT. But in case of doubt, consult the FORTRAN files: TPPLLOT.FTN and TEKPLT.FTN for Apollo, with TPPLLOTKOM.INS.FTN being the INCLUDE file that defines the indices.

Index	Name	Default	Function of the REAL variable; rules of its use
6.	TAXISL	10.0	Time axis length in inches for both screen and CalComp plots.
7.	TOLRCE	8.E-5	The square of the maximum error in inches, for the discarding of data points to speed plotting.
8.	HTAX	4.0	Height of the horizontal (time) axis in inches for "COPY" (CalComp) usage.
9.	XTIT	0.5	The 80-column, multi-line case title is indented this many inches from the left edge of a "COPY" (CalComp) plot.
10.	YTIT	8.5	Like XTIT, only for height above the bottom of plot, in inches.
11.	SIZTIT	0.12	Height of lettering, in inches, for the multi-line case title of a "COPY" (CalComp) plot.

12.	XSUPER	1.00	The single-line super title is indented this many inches from the left edge of a "COPY" (CalComp) plot.
13.	YSUPER	0.60	Like XSUPER, only for height above the bottom of plot, in inches.
14.	SIZSUP	0.30	Height of lettering, in inches, for the super title of a "COPY" (CalComp) plot.
16.	SIZID	0.17	Height in inches of the lettering that is used for the case title, etc. of a "COPY" (CalComp) plot.
17.	XID	0.5	The plot file identification line (date/time) is indented this many inches from the left edge of a "COPY" (CalComp) plot.
18.	YID	0.75	Like YID, only for height above the bottom of plot, in inches.
19.	FACT	1.0	Magnification factor for plot. The use of unity is for measurements in inches. To use metric (see "METRIC" request), change to 0.7874 so half-inch marks are changed to centimeter marks.
20.	DXGRD1	1.0	X-direction inches spacing of 1st "COPY" grid.
21.	DYGRD1	1.0	Y-direction inches spacing of 1st "COPY" grid.
22.	DXGRD2	0.2	X-direction inches spacing of 2nd "COPY" grid.
23.	DYGRD2	0.2	Y-direction inches spacing of 2nd "COPY" grid.
32.	FHTAX	0.5	Height of time axis of screen plot: the fraction along the Y-axis if there is no zero level for it.
33.	FXSUP	0.3	Fractional displacement along the X-axis, to the right of the Y-axis, for the start of the super title line. This is for screen plots only.
34.	FYSUP	-.03	Fractional displacement along the Y-axis, for the super title. This is for screen plots only. The sign depends on the computer and/or plot software, as does the direction of the measurement (from bottom to top, or vice versa).
35.	FXTIT	0.10	Fractional displacement along the X-axis, to the right of the Y-axis, for the start of the multi-line case title. This is for screen plots only.
36.	FYTIT	0.15	Fractional displacement along the Y-axis, for the case title. This is for screen plots only. The sign depends on the computer and/or plot software, as does the direction of the measurement (from bottom to top, or vice versa).
39.	FTCARR	1.0	Multiplying factor for interline spacing of lines of text on a screen plot. Unity means single spacing, since the actual pixels equal this factor times the character height in pixels.
40.	VAXISL	8.0	Length of the Y-axis in inches, for a screen plot.
41.	FXNUMV	1.5	The number of lines below X-axis for placement of X-axis numbers of a screen plot.
42.	FXNUMH	5.0	The X-axis numbers of a screen plot begin this many bytes to left of the X-axis tic marks.
43.	FVAXTT	-7.5	The Y-axis label of a screen plot is to be located this many bytes to the right of the Y-axis itself.
44.	FXVERT	0.0	The fraction along the X-axis for placement of the Y-axis of an X-Y screen plot. Zero is taken to mean a request for placement of the Y-axis at the value $X=0$, if such a zero crossing occurs.
45.	FSYMB	0.83	The power frequency in Hertz for cycles, degrees.
46.	FPOWER	60.0	The power frequency in Hertz for cycles, degrees.

Index	Name	Default	Function of the INTEGER variable; rules of its use
1.	KLEVL	0	Binary flag to select whether level crossings of plot variables are to be calculated. Zero means no such calculation, whereas unity requests it.
2.	KEXTR	0	Binary flag to select whether extrema of plot variables are to be calculated. Zero means no such calculation, whereas unity requests it.
3.	IHS	3	Integer code for time units being used: [seconds]. The common alternative is "4" for milliseconds.
9.	LTEK	3	A binary switch that chooses between character plotting and vector-graphic plotting for screen plots.
11.	NUMSYM	3	Number of times each curve will be marked with an identifying symbol. This applies to both "COPY" (CalComp) and screen plots.
13.	MAXISX	3	Pen width for the X-axis structure of a "COPY" (CalComp) plot. Use "0" to suppress the X-axis and associated labels.
14.	MAXISY	3	Like MAXISX, only for the Y-axis of "COPY" plot.
15.	MGRID1	0	Pen width for 1st "COPY" (CalComp) grid. This is the outer, coarse grid. Use "0" to suppress it.
16.	MGRID2	0	Pen width for 2nd "COPY" (CalComp) grid. This is the inner, fine grid. Use "0" to suppress it.
17.	MSUPER	5	Pen width for super title of a "COPY" (CalComp) plot. Use "0" to suppress the super title.
22.	NSMTH	50	Limit on consecutive ups and downs before the commencement of averaging of successive ordinates.
23.	LSYMB	1	Binary flag that controls the table of curve marking symbols (and % of data points used) for a screen plot. To suppress this table, use "0".
26.	LCHID	2	Tektronix PLOT10-like size code for the date/time line lettering. This is an argument of "CHRSIZ".
27.	NXINCH	71	Pixels/inch in X direction for screen plot. This figure is for a 19-inch Apollo with landscape display of resolution 800 x 1024. For the 17-inch DN3XX screens, use something closer to 80.
28.	NYINCH	72	Pixels/inch in Y direction for screen plot. This figure is for a 19-inch Apollo with landscape display of resolution 800 x 1024. For the 17-inch DN3XX screens, use something closer to 85.
29.	NXOFF	100	The Y-axis is located this many pixels to the right of the left edge, for a vector screen plot.
30.	NYOFF	40	The top or bottom of the Y-axis of a vector plot has this pixel address. It will be the top if pixel addresses increase downward (as for Apollo GPR). Otherwise, it will be the bottom.
32.	LCHSUP	3	Tektronix PLOT10-like size code for the super-title lettering. It is also used for the X-axis labeling. The variable is an argument of "CHRSIZ" used only for vector screen plots.
33.	LCHTIT	2	Tektronix PLOT10-like size code for the multiline case title. It is also used for the axis numbers. The variable is an argument of "CHRSIZ", used only for vector screen plots.

34.	LCHXAX	0	Control variable for the presence or absence of the X-axis and its labeling on a vector screen plot. The value "-1" will suppress everything, whereas "0" will result in labeling without the axis or tic marks. Finally, "+1" will produce both the axis and the associated labeling.
35.	LCHYAX	0	Tektronix PLOT10-like size code for the Y-axis and its labeling. The variable is an argument of "CHRSIZ", used only for vector screen plots. A value of zero will suppress the Y-axis itself while retaining the labeling. A value of "-1" will suppress everything, whereas a value "+1" will produce both the Y-axis and its labeling.
37.	LTIC	7	Half the pixel width of the 2-sided tic marks for the axes of a screen plot.
39	IZGR1	-1	To suppress the first (outer) background grid of a vector screen plot, key this value as "-1". Whether any positive value other than "1" has special meaning in terms of boldness of the grid will depend on the program version being used.
40.	IZGR2	-1	Like variable IZGR1, only for 2nd (inner) grid.
45.	NXID6	100	X-pixels for the beginning of the date/time line below the vector screen plot. This figure is to the right of the left edge of plot.
46.	NYID6	620	Y-pixels for the beginning of the date/time line below the vector screen plot.
50.	NXVERN	70	The number of pixels to the right of the left edge of a vector screen plot, for the beginning (left edge) of Y-axis numbers.
53.	INCHPX	2	The placement frequency for X-axis numbers that accompany axis tic marks of a vector screen plot. The value "2" means numbers will appear for every 2nd inch mark.
54.	INCHPY	2	Similar to variable INCHPX, only for the Y-axis.
57.	LCHFIL	1	Binary control over appearance of the line of "PL4." plot-file identification (date/time), and also the following line of plot variable names. To suppress the associated output, use the value zero instead of unity.
58.	LCHLIM	1	Code controlling appearance of the line of time-axis limits and scaling of a "COPY" (CalComp) plot. Use "+1" to see such a line, and "-1" to suppress such output.

"COLUMN" and "SET COLUMN" are used only for character plots, to control the width (number of characters) being used. The first command toggles the switch that chooses between 80 and 132-column character plots. The second allows for other widths (there will be a subsequent prompt for the desired value).

"STOP" will terminate execution cleanly with a closure of all files. For most computers, this is not necessary, and it probably is easier for the user simply to abort execution by whatever means the operating system provides. But this caused trouble (e.g., a failure to close I/O channels) for some computers, so a clean termination is also provided.

"EXTREMA" is used to toggle the switch that decides whether or not variable extrema of subsequent plots are to be printed as a separate tabulation preceding the associate plot. Following such possible output, the program will pause before drawing the graph. If the user sends a <CR>, the graph will follow. Alternatively, the user can send "NO PLOT" to bypass the subsequent plot completely.

"LEVEL" is like "EXTREMA" only it applies to level crossings. If such output is being turned on, there will be a prompt for a vector of desired levels, to which the user should respond in free-format.

"COPY" will dispatch a just-completed plot (either character or vector) to the CalComp (or imitation CalComp) plotter. The program will respond with a request for a revised time-axis scaling. Once the new dt/inch figure is sent (or blank, to leave this scaling unaltered, the CalComp plot will automatically be produced. When the CalComp plot is done, the prompt "PLOT:" will reappear.

"X-Y PLOT" will toggle the binary switch that chooses between regular plotting of variables as functions of time and the less common plotting of one variable against another with time as a parameter of the resulting locus. The program will begin in conventional (non-XY) mode, of course.

"CURSOR" initiates dialogue involving the cursor to identify points of user interest on the screen. But few systems will use this. It depends not only on computer, but also on the terminal or monitor being used. Check with program maintenance.

"AVERAGE" adjusts the oscillation limit after which averaging of successive ordinates of a curve will be instituted. This is generally useful only in cases having artificial numerical oscillation about the true value due to trouble with trapezoidal rule integration.

"SMOOTH" allows the user to redefine the tolerance for discarding plot data points. Why are any data points discarded? The issue is plotting speed and storage: less memory is used, and it is faster, if the graphical output is minimized. Many curves are sufficiently smooth so that most data points can be omitted without the user being able to observe the difference. The default tolerance should be set to correspond to the visual limit of the plotting device, or the engineering application. See variable TOLRCE (REAL index 7 of "SET DATA"). The lower right hand corner of a vector screen plot should (for most computers) display statistics about the effectiveness of point discarding. Beside the symbols for each curve will be first the total number of points actually plotted, and second, the percentage that this is of the total available points. For example: "a --- 356 23%". If the tolerance TOLRCE is set to zero, this percentage should approach 100, of course.

"BOLD" allows the user to change the boldness of curves of a vector screen plot. A value of zero means that plotting will be done with minimum pixel width. A positive value is interpreted as the excess width in pixels on each side of the normal line segments that define the curve. That is, a rectangle is actually drawn, and the width of this will be twice the pixel width requested by the user in response to a subsequent prompt:

SEND PIXEL WIDTH OF EACH SIDE :

To suppress such bold drawing, key zero.

"COLOR" is the request to change the colors used for the curves of each window of a vector screen plot. There will be a subsequent prompt for two integers:

Old color codes for screen plot = 1 2 3 4 5 ...

SEND BEGINNING INDEX AND VECTOR LENGTH :

The user is allowed to redefine a contiguous range of curve colors, with the first index of the range, and the length of the range, being defined here. Then a subsequent prompt will allow the user to redefine the requested colors:

SEND VECTOR OF ALTERED COLORS :

"DOT" is the request to turn on or off dots (more precisely, disks) that mark each plot data point after the discarding of points by "SMOOTH". A prompt will then request the size of the disks:

SEND RADIUS OF CIRCLE IN PIXELS [0] :

Use zero to suppress such marking, whereas a positive value is interpreted as the radius of the disk (to be filled with the color of the curve) in pixels.

I-L-2. WINDOWPLT --- for simpler, multiple-window, plotting

Program "WINDOWPLT" is designed to display many curves on the same screen or piece of paper. The name comes from "window plotting," which emphasizes the dominant attraction. The user is allowed up to 9 independent plot windows that are stacked vertically one on top of the other. Each of these windows has an independent display, although the time scales (horizontal axes) of all must be the same. Needless to say, only vector-graphic plotting is allowed (the character mode is hopelessly short of resolution for typical usage). Both vector-graphic monitor plots and CalComp hard-copy plots are available.

For flexible computers such as Apollo, there seems to be no limit on the total height of these stacked plots if they are written to the screen. But this is only possible because Apollo windows can be scrolled vertically. For less intelligent displays (e.g., the popular, old, storage-tube devices of Tektronix, such as the 19-inch 4014), the user will be limited to the height of the screen, should output be directed to the screen. Consult installation-dependent instructions of Section I-F for specifics. As for hard copy (paper) output, present logic limits this to the width of the paper, since the time axis runs the length of the paper (for roll plotters such as Versatek printer/plotters, or CalComp drum plotters).

Program "WINDOWPLT" is in fact just a special version of the regular interactive plotting program "TPPLOT" of the preceding subsection I-L-1. It is less sophisticated in that some of the features of the original logic are unavailable. Specifically, the "MENU" display shows restriction to the following:

```
>>> PLOT :MENU
List of all possible command words follows ...
ALL TIME CHOICE DEBUG ERASE SHOW WINDOWS
GO HELP FILE TIMESPAN TIME UNITS
MENU MODE NAME SHOW CURVES LABEL
PURGE REFILE TIME SET DATA STOP
COLOR
```

Since most of these commands have already been explained in the preceding subsection I-L-1, the explanation here shall be limited to new commands only:

"W?" is a request to begin the specification of window number "?" (a single decimal digit between unity "1" and "9"). By definition, windows are numbered from top to bottom of the screen or paper, in natural order. Yet numbers need not be consecutive (unused or inactive window numbers can be skipped without difficulty). The "W?" request will be acknowledged by a sequence of six prompts as follows:

- 1) Old 1-line window title = { A80 }
SEND NEW (<CR>=>accept; ERASE; ACTIVE) :
- 2) Old Y-axis label = { A80 }
SEND NEW (<CR>=>accept; ERASE) :
- 3) Vertical axis minimum and maximum = { 2E14.6 }
SEND NEW (<CR>=>accept; 0,0) :
- 4) Window height and separation = { 2E14.6 }
SEND NEW (<CR>=>accept) :
- 5) Y-axis units and numbers = { 2I5 }
SEND NEW (<CR>=>accept) :
- 6) Curves [{ 9I3 }
SEND NUMBER CURVES (<CR>=>accept) :
- 7) SEND NEW CURVE NUMBERS :

Note that the first five prompts involve two lines each, with the first of the two lines describing what is required of the user, and showing the existing (old) content that can be reused if just a carriage return (<CR>) is keyed by the user. Following a display of all old curve numbers of the window, prompt 6 demands the new number of curves NUMC to be plotted in the window. Finally, prompt 7 asks for a string of NUMC new curve numbers (from the input order of the preceding variable selection by "NAME"). Just as with input of the conventional "TPPLOT", a single usage of "NAME" requests all plot variables. The difference is that now these variables can be allocated arbitrarily among multiple windows. Also, any variable can be plotted in two or more different windows, if desired.

"SHOW WINDOWS" (or simply "SHOW W" in abbreviated form) is a command to display the parameters associated with each window that the user has defined. The 2-line heading of the resulting display, along with an entry for window number 1, are illustrated as follows (truncated on the right):

First curve	Number curves	Y-axis limits	Window height	Window spacing	Window Y axis min	Window Y axis max	Y-axis units	Y-curve nu
@@@ Window 1. Title =First window case title line								
2	2	0	4.00	1.00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00		4

The zero in the 3rd column ("Y-axis limits") means that vertical scaling will be done automatically by the program, so the "min" and "max" entries to the right are to be ignored (note that both are zero). The first column ("First curve") will be negative if the window is defined but inactive (see the "ERASE" command).

"SHOW CURVES" (or simply "SHOW C" in abbreviated form) is a command to summarize the plot variables that have already been selected during the most recent preceding "NAME" request. Whereas not necessary for window plotting, this is just an added diagnostic tool to simplify life for the user. Most importantly, the output will show variable numbers (as required for the "W?" command). As an illustration, consider the display associated with all 4 variables to the test plot file HMMSS.PL4 produced by program "PLOTDAT":

```
>>> PLOT :SHOW C
```

```
LASTNODEV, LASTBRANV, NAMVAR, JPLT = 2 4 6 4
```

1. Node voltage for node "NODE1 ". Variable MPLOT = 2
2. Node voltage for node "NODE2 ". Variable MPLOT = 1
3. Branch voltage "NODE1 " to "NODE2 ". Variable MPLOT = 3
4. Branch current "NODE2 " to "NODE3 ". Variable MPLOT = 4

The MPLOT number on the right is the position in the output vector (not normally of interest to the user).

"MODE" allows for the selection of output device: screen, or paper, or both. Unlike "TPPLOT", there is no "COPY" command to produce hard copy after the screen plot. Instead, the selection must be made before plotting begins. Consider the following illustration:

```
>>> PLOT :MODE
```

```
Vector plot modes: 1=screen; 2=CalComp; 3=both.
```

```
SUPPLY MODE [ 1 ] :
```

Shown within square brackets is the present mode of output (unity for screen-only plotting, for this example) that is about to be changed.

"ERASE" will deactivate all windows without actually destroying or losing any parameter specifications of them. Recall that there are 9 possible windows. When program execution begins, all 9 windows are both undefined and inactive. Activity of a window is indicated by a positive number for the 1st curve of the window. What the erase command does is replace all such numbers (for all windows) to the negatives of the absolute values. Inactive windows will show up in the "SHOW WINDOWS" display as having a negative integer in the first column on the left. To reactivate a previously-deactivated window, identify the window via a "W?" command, and then send "ACTIVE" in response to the first subprompt.

"SET DATA" functions the same way as already described for "TPPLOT". However, a different plotting program is involved, and the INCLUDE file defining the control variables and their associated indices, WINDOWKOM.INS.FTN (for Apollo), differs somewhat. The following table applies:

Index	Name	Default	Function of the REAL variable; rules of its use
6.	TAXISL	10.0	Time axis length in inches for both screen and CalComp plots.
7.	TOLRCE	8.E-5	The square of the maximum error in inches, for the discarding of data points to speed plotting.
9.	XTIT	2.5	The window title line is to begin this many inches to the right of the left edge of a CalComp plot.
11.	SIZTIT	0.12	Height of multi-line case title for CalComp plot.
13.	XOFFAX	0.60	The Y-axis of a CalComp plot is located this many inches to the right of the left edge of the page.
16.	SIZID	0.17	Height in inches of the lettering that is used for the case title, etc. of a CalComp plot.
17.	XID	1.8	The plot file identification line (date/time) is indented this many inches from the left edge of a CalComp plot.
20.	DXGRD1	1.0	X-direction inches spacing of 1st CalComp grid
21.	DYGRD1	1.0	Y-direction inches spacing of 1st CalComp grid
22.	DXGRD2	0.2	X-direction inches spacing of 2nd CalComp grid
23.	DYGRD2	0.2	Y-direction inches spacing of 2nd CalComp grid
32.	FHTAX	0.5	Height of time axis of screen plot: fraction along the Y-axis if there is no zero level for it.
33.	FXSUP	0.3	Fractional displacement along the X-axis, to the right of the Y-axis, for the start of window title line. This is for screen plots only, not CalComp.
39.	FTCARR	1.3	The number of lines that the time-axis label is below the time axis itself, for a screen plot.
41.	FXNUMV	1.5	The number of lines below X-axis for placement of X-axis numbers of a screen plot.
43.	FVAXTT	-9.5	The Y-axis label of a screen plot is to be located this many bytes to the right of the Y-axis itself.
42.	FXNUMH	5.0	The number of characters to the left of the time-axis tic mark for the beginning of an associated numerical time value of a screen plot.
46.	FPOWER	60.0	The power frequency in Hertz for cycles, degrees.

Index	Name	Default	Function of the INTEGER variable; rules of its use
2.	JMODE	1	Ternary (3) integer code to select the mode of plotting. "1" is for Screen plotting only, "2" is for CalComp only, and "3" is for both.
3.	IHS	3	Integer code for time units being used: [seconds]. The common alternative is "4" for milliseconds.
11.	NUMSYM	3	Number of times each curve will be marked with an identifying symbol. This applies to both CalComp and screen plots.
13.	MAXISX	1	Binary switch controlling whether a CalComp plot will have an X-axis or not. Use "1" if the X-axis is wanted, or "0" to suppress it.
14.	MAXISY	1	Like variable MAXISX, only for CalComp Y-axis.
15.	MGRID1	1	Binary switch controlling whether the course first CalComp grid is wanted. Use "1" to request such a grid, or "0" to suppress it.
16.	MGRID2	1	Binary switch controlling whether the fine second CalComp grid is wanted. Use "1" to request such a grid, or "0" to suppress it.
22.	NSMTH	50	Limit on consecutive ups and downs before the commencement of averaging of successive ordinates.
27.	NXINCH	71	Pixels/inch in X direction for screen plot. This figure is for a 19-inch Apollo with landscape display of resolution 800 x 1024. For the 17-inch DN3XX screens, use something closer to 80.
28.	NYINCH	72	Pixels/inch in Y direction for screen plot. This figure is for a 19-inch Apollo with landscape display of resolution 800 x 1024. For the 17-inch DN3XX screens, use something closer to 85.
29.	NXOFF	142	The Y-axis is located this many pixels to the right of the left edge of a screen plot.
30.	NYOFF	5	The window title line is to be located this many pixels from the top of the window grid. This will be above the top of the grid (or upper end of the Y-axis) if pixel addresses increase downward (as for Apollo GPR). Otherwise, it will be below.
32.	LCHSUP	3	Tektronix PLOT10-like size code for the super-title lettering. This is an argument of "CHRSIZ".
33.	LCHFIT	2	Tektronix PLOT10-like size code for the multiline case title. This is an argument of "CHRSIZ".
34.	LCHXAX	2	Tektronix PLOT10-like size code for the time-axis numbering and units labeling of the bottom window only of a screen plot. This is an argument of "CHRSIZ". To suppress such labeling, use the value "-1".
35.	LCHYAX	2	Like variable LCHXAX (34), only for the Y-axis.
37.	LTIC	7	Half the pixel width of the 2-sided tic marks for the axes of a screen plot.
39	IZGR1	-1	To suppress the first (outer) background grid of a screen plot, key this value as "-1". Whether any positive value other than "1" has special meaning in terms of boldness of the grid will depend on the program version being used.

40.	IZGR2	-1	Like IZGR1 (39), only for the 2nd (inner) grid.
45.	NXID6	130	X-pixels for the beginning of the date/time line below the bottom window of a screen plot. This figure is to the right of the left edge of plot.
50.	NXVERN	70	The number of pixels to the right of the left edge of a screen plot, for the beginning (left edge) of Y-axis numbers.
53.	INCHPX	2	The placement frequency for X-axis numbers that accompany axis tic marks of a screen plot. The value "2" means numbers will appear for every 2nd inch mark.
54.	INCHPY	2	Like variable INCHPX (53), only for the Y-axis.
57.	LCHFIL	2	Tektronix PLOT10-like size code for the "PL4." plot file identification (date/time). This is used as an argument of "CHRSIZ". To suppress such labeling, use the value "-1".
58.	LCHLIM	1	Code controlling appearance of the line of time-axis limits and scaling of a CalComp plot. Use "+1" to see such a line, and "-1" to suppress such output.
59.	LCHNAM	2	Tektronix PLOT10-like size code for the line of plot variable names. This is an argument of "CHRSIZ". To suppress such labeling, use the value "-1".

Although "WINDOWPLT" is an interactive program, with prompts designed for the screen, most production usage will be in the batch mode. This is done via files of prestored input. An example of four such screen plots, and one CalComp (paper) plot, can be found in the disk file WINDOWPLT.DAT (the name used for Apollo). Note that both comment cards (beginning with "C", just as for EMTP data) and in-line comments (to the right of "{") are allowed. Whereas the interactive user would seldom key such explanation, the batch-mode user is encouraged to document his input this way. To see a demonstration of most features, simply execute the contents of WINDOWPLT.DAT by pasting the contents into the input pane of a window that is full height and nearly full width. Then sit back, relax, and watch the action! To avoid noticeable delays of input, use a plot file (produced by PLOTDAT.FTN) with few data points (e.g., 10 or 20).

I-L-3. MS-DOS Interactive Plotting Program PCPLOT by Mustafa Kizilcay

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1. About PCPLOT

~ PCPLOT is a separate interactive plotting program to produce vector-graphic plots of the EMTP (version ATP) results stored in the "*.PL4" plot data files. PCPLOT can be used with following types of *.PL4 files:

- Unformatted PL4-files created by Lahey (F77L) compilation of IBM PC-version of ATP. (L4BYTE=0 in STARTUP file)
- Transparent (C-like) PL4-files created by Lahey (F77L) compilation of IBM PC-version of ATP. (L4BYTE=1 in STARTUP file)
- Unformatted PL4-files created by Salford's FTN77/386 compilation of 386 PC-version of ATP.
- Formatted PL4-files created by any version of ATP. Warning. This beta test version (Dec, 89) fails to plot some (e.g., DC3TO54.PL4).

~ Automatic detection of PL4-file type.

~ PCPLOT was produced using Borland's Turbo Pascal compiler (version 5.0) under MS-DOS 3.30.

~ Possible plot types are:

- time function : results of the EMTP simulations
- xy-plot : one variable against another
- frequency-response : results of "FREQUENCY SCAN" cases.

~ Elimination of the visually redundant plot data points depending on the smoothing tolerance defined in pixels.

~ PCPLOT can plot maximum three curves with 16000 plot points per curve after automatic point elimination.

~ The maximum number of plot variables stored in the plot file is limited to 100.

~ The values of the plotted variables can be displayed on the screen at the position marked on the x-axis by means of a vertical marker line.

~ The graphic adapters Hercules (monochrome), CGA, EGA and VGA are supported.

~ Automatic detection of graphics adapter used.

- ~ A hardcopy of the screen plot can be obtained using any Epson-compatible 8-pin or 24-pin dot-matrix printer in two different sizes.
- ~ The commands are assigned to the function keys in order to save typing words.
- ~ Commands and data for PCPLOT can be entered from a batch-job file instead of from the keyboard.
- ~ Emulation of coprocessors 8087, 80287 or 80387, if not present.
- ~ Certain options can be defined in an ASCII-configuration file PCPLOT.INI.
- ~ Case titles (max. 3 lines) can be saved in a *.TI4 file, where the first 8 characters of the file name is the same as *.PL4 file.

2 System Requirements

2.1 Software

- ~ Operating system: MS-DOS or PC-DOS version 3.0 or higher (also 4.0).
- ~ Configuration file PCPLOT.INI. If it is not present in the current directory, default options will be used.

2.2 Hardware

- ~ IBM XT, AT, 386 - compatible PC
- ~ IBM PS/2
- ~ Graphic adapter:
 - Hercules Graphic Card (HGC) Resolution: 720 x 348 pixels
 - Color Graphic Adapter (CGA) 640 x 200 pixels
 - Enhanced Graphic Adapter (EGA) 640 x 350 pixels
 - Video Graphics Array (VGA) 640 x 480 pixels
- ~ (optional) Epson-compatible 8-pin or 24-pin dot-matrix printer. (Epson MX-, RX-, FX- or LQ-series, NEC P5/P6/P7, Star LC(24)-10)

3 Installing PCPLOT --- Unnecessary for those who have it.

4 Starting PCPLOT

Type PCPLOT and press <CR>. The first page of the program will be displayed (See next chapter).

The error message

"PCPLOT.INI" corrupted. Default values will be used.

implies that number of lines in PCPLOT.INI is different than as expected by PCPLOT.

4.1 Configuration file PCPLOT.INI

 The configuration file PCPLOT.INI is an ASCII-file that can be modified using any text editor. Like STARTUP of ATP, every comment line is followed by a data line. If there is a mismatch between the length of PCPLOT.INI and the lines expected by PCPLOT, then an error message is displayed and default values of the configuration variables are used. The same default values will be used, when PCPLOT.INI is missing in the working directory. Preceding comment lines describe following data lines in PCPLOT.INI.

Contents of PCPLOT.INI:

1. data line: One of the following PL4-file types should be selected:
 ----- 0: unformatted PL4-file created by IBM PC-DOS version of ATP (L4BYTE=0 in STARTUP).
 1: C-like, unformatted PL4-file. Set L4BYTE=1 in STARTUP file for IBM PC-DOS version of ATP.
 2: unformatted PL4-file created by 386-Salford version of ATP.
 3: formatted PL4-files created by any version of ATP.
 99: automatic detection of PL4-file types given above.

Default: 99

2. data line: Parallel-port (LPT1) of your printer connected.
 ----- Default: 1

3. data line: Serial-port (COM1) of your HP-plotter connected.
 ----- Default: 1

4. data line: Width of hardcopy on paper:
 ----- 1: 21 cm (8 inches)
 2: 28 cm (11 inches)

Default: 1

5. data line: Flag to store plot title in *.TI4-file (ASCII).
 ----- 0: no such storage of 3-line plot title in a *.TI4 file.
 1: save 3-line plot title in an ASCII, *.TI4 file.
 The file name is the same of PL4-file, only the extension is different.

Default: 0

5. Using PCPLOT

PCPLOT consists of three pages (levels). As you proceed to produce a screen plot, each page (level) will be passed sequentially. At each level it is possible to return to the previous levels or exit from the program. The user dialog to produce a plot is rather simple and self-explanatory. The prompts of the program and error messages always appear at line 22. Lines 24 and 25 are used to display the possible commands at that page of the program. The commands are assigned to the function-keys in order to save the work of typing. Activities and commands at each level are:

5.1 Page #1

~ <CR> : File Name

Pressing <CR> results in a prompt to enter a plot file name. The complete file name with the search path or the number of the file assigned by activating F2:Directory command is accepted. A "#" must precede the number of a file, in order to distinguish it from the name. In case of entering name of a file, the search path need not be typed, if the directory of the plot file has been listed by F2:Directory command before. The file name extension ".PL4" may not be given. It will be appended automatically to the file name, if it is missing.

~ F1 : Help

Pressing F1-key results in displaying one-page description of commands of this page of PCPLOT.

~ F2 : Directory

"*.PL4" files in a directory will be listed on the screen, when F2-key is pressed and a complete search path is entered. To each plot file name displayed on the screen a number will be assigned. In order to list the current directory press F2 and <CR>. The last search path is saved, so that pressing F2 and <CR> results in displaying the last directory selected.

~ F3 : Batch Job

Commands and data for PCPLOT are entered from an existing ascii-file instead of from the keyboard. The batch job begins at the first level of the program by attaching the plot file and ends at the third level in the screen plot. When during the batch run an error occurs, the input will be linked from the batch job-file to the keyboard, so that the user can continue interactively. A batch job-file is created according to the following rules. Enter data by beginning always from the first column.

- 1.line : Name of the plot file with the complete search path.
- 2.line : Plot type. Enter one of the numbers
1 : time function
2 : xy-plot
3 : frequency response
- 3.line : Maximum three curve numbers seperated by comma. The curves are numbered in the same order as they appear in the output list of EMTP. These curve numbers are displayed on the second page of the program (file contents). If plot type = 2 (xy-plot) is selected, then the first curve number will represent x-variable and max. two plot variables can be plotted against the first one.
- 4.line : Smoothing tolerance defined in pixels. Blank sets the default value 0.90.

5-6.lines: The user can predefine the bounds of the independent plot variable, time or frequency. This is useful, if the plot file contains too many points (> 16000 after point elimination) or a special part of the plot is of interest. Min. value of the independent variable is followed by the max. value. Leave the corresponding line blank, if original bound is desired.

7.line : This data line is only necessary, if plot type 2 or 3 has been selected. Otherwise, skip this line.
Plot type = 2 : Enter one-character symbol and unit (max. 4 characters) of the x-axis seperated by comma. See page #3-explanations for more information.
Plot type = 3 : Enter "A", if the frequency response has been computed using arithmetic spacing of frequency points. Enter "G", if the frequency response has been computed using geometric spacing of frequency points.

8.line : Enter one-character symbol and unit (max. 4 characters) of the y-axis seperated by comma.

9-10.lines: Three lines plot title with max. 70 characters per line. Insert blank lines, if you do not want to enter plot title.

Repeat the lines 1 to 9 above as often as is desired. Each such group of data represents an independent batch job, which will be processed sequentially. Having finished plotting activities (hardcopy, display value,...) at the third page of the program, the user should press F3:New Case to return to the first level and strike F3:Batch Job and <CR> to start the next batch run from the same file.

~ F10 : Quit
Leave PCPLOT.

5.2 Page #2

At this level of PCPLOT the plot variables will be listed in three columns.

~ <CR> : Select
Pressing <CR> results in a prompt to select the plot type. Enter one of the numbers

1 : time function
2 : xy-plot
3 : frequency response.

The user is responsible for selecting the right plot type, that should be in agreement with the case computed. A prompt will follow to select curves, which are desired on the same plot. Thereafter the plot data are read through to search for the min. and max. values of all variables and are stored in a temporary Turbo Pascal file in order to speed up reading the plot data of the selected variables by using this temporary file.

~ F1 : Help

Pressing F1-key results in displaying one-page description of commands of this page of PCPLOT.

~ F2 : Window

The user can predefine the bounds of the independent plot variable, time or frequency. This is useful, when the plot file contains too many points (greater than 16000 points after point elimination). By entering min. and max. value for the independent variable a window is defined. This window is displayed in proportion to the whole length of the plot. The user can enlarge this window on the screen using F5-key of page #3. The original bound will be set, when <CR> is pressed. If the given values are out of range, they are replaced by the original bounds.

~ F3 : New Case

Return to the first page of PCPLOT to select a new plot file or to start a new batch job.

~ F4 : Smoothing

The smoothing tolerance has to be entered in units of screen pixels. Depending on its value, the visually redundant points will be discarded. Smoothing tolerance is the maximum allowable distance of a point to the line defined by the last two plot points allocated. Default value 0.9 pixel is selected, when <CR> is pressed. Note that when 0.0 is entered, points can still be eliminated, if they lie on a straight line.

~ F5 : Review

Pressing F5-key results in displaying file contents again.

~ F10 : Quit

Leave PCPLOT.

5.3 Page #3

The plot will be displayed and axis label has to be entered by the user. There are some commonly used predefined units. If one of them is entered, an one-character symbol will lead it. X-axis will be labeled automatically, if plot type = 1 or 3 has been selected. The power of 10 of the scaling numbers as a multiple of three is represented between (-9..+9) by the characters n ($10^{**(-9)}$), f ($10^{**(-6)}$), m ($10^{**(-3)}$), k ($10^{**(3)}$), M ($10^{**(6)}$), G ($10^{**(9)}$). If the power of 10 is out of range given above, then it will be represented as usual (10 to power). The character defining the power of 10 will lead the unit of that axis. This character and max. 4 characters given as the unit are included in the squared brackets. The user can define both one-character symbol and the corresponding unit (max. four characters) for an axis or he can enter a predefined unit and the corresponding one-character symbol will be selected automatically. The format of an axis label is:

x [yzzzz] or x [10n*zzzz] for |n| > 9

where

x : one-character symbol

y : one of the characters n, f, m, k, M, G
representing the power of 10

zzzz: unit of an axis (max. four characters)

n : integer representing the power for |n| > 9.

The predefined one-character symbols and the corresponding units are:

t, sec	: time, second	T, Nm	: torque, newton-m
v, V	: voltage, volt	r, j	: resistance, ohm
i, A	: current, ampere	g, mho	: conductance, mho
P, W	: power, watt	f, Hz	: frequency, hertz
W, J	: energy, joule	f, lgHz	: frequency, log ₁₀ (f) hertz
\, x	: angle, degree		

Example: The label of the y-axis will be displayed as i [kA], if "A" is entered as the unit. "k" stands for 10**3 as the scale factor. The symbol "i" and "k" will be selected automatically by the program. The special characters j, x will be displayed, if you type "ohm" and "grad" respectively.

~ F1 : Help

Pressing F1-key results in displaying one-page description of commands of this page of PCPLOT.

~ F2 : Contents

Return to the second page of PCPLOT in order to select new variables to plot.

~ F3 : New Case

Return to the first page of PCPLOT.

~ F4 : Hardcopy

Only Epson-compatible printers are supported by PCPLOT. Owners of 24-pin printers can choose between 8-pin and 24-pin hardcopy. Producing hardcopy by a 24-pin printer using 24-pin option is slow but of better quality. 24-pin printers, Epson LQ-series, NEC P5/P6/P7 and Star LC24-10 are used satisfactorily to produce hardcopy.

If your printer is connected to parallel-port 2 (LPT2), then modify the corresponding data line in configuration file PCPLOT.INI.

Two different widths (21 cm, 28 cm) of hardcopy on paper are supported. The desired width is selected in PCPLOT.INI: 1 --> 21 cm, 2 --> 28 cm.

When the result of the hardcopy is unsatisfactory for the printer used, an external memory-resident graphic hardcopy program can be used while running the plotting program. There are several cheap graphic hardcopy programs for widely-used brands of printers available. Follow the steps given below to use any external memory-resident graphic hardcopy program, provided that the screen plot has already been produced:

1. Press F4 (Hardcopy)
2. Press "A" or "B" (of no consequence)
3. Press any key other than <CR> to display the complete plot
4. Activate your own hardcopy program by means of key sequences
5. When hardcopy is finished, press <CR>
6. Send "n" to skip the hardcopy of the plotting program.

Note: When alternating blank lines appear on a hardcopy, then the printer switch settings are not correct. In this case refer to your printer manual and change the setting of the switch concerning carriage return and line feed.

~ F5 : X-Range

Enter the desired limits of the x-axis to zoom in/out the plot horizontally. Visually redundant plot data points are eliminated for the new window of the plot. Entering "?" for the min. and max. values results in a plot with the original horizontal bounds.

~ F6 : Y-Range

Enter the desired limits of the y-axis to zoom in/out the plot vertically. Visually redundant plot data points are eliminated for the new window of the plot. Entering "?" for the min. and max. values results in a plot with original vertical bounds.

~ F7 : Plot Title

Maximum three lines text up to the 74 characters can be entered. The plot title will be printed at the bottom of the plot, when hardcopy is obtained. The plot title can be saved in an ASCII-file automatically, if the user selects this option in PCPLOT.INI. The name of this file is the same as of the corresponding PL4-file, but the extension is "TI4". If such a *.TI4 file is missing, it will be created automatically, provided the user enters a plot title. If TI4-file is present in the directory, then the contents will be shown, when F7-key is pressed.

~ F10 : Quit

Leave PCPLOT.

~ Displaying values of the plot variables:

A dashed, vertical marker line will be moved on the screen horizontally by pressing arrow-keys <-, -> to show the values of the plot variables at the position marked on the x-axis. The jump length of the marker line can be altered by pressing Page-Up (jumps become longer) or Page-Down (jumps become shorter) -keys. The marker line will be moved to the left edge of the plot, if Home-key is pressed and it will be moved to the right edge, if End-key is struck.

I-L. \$PARAMETER to Define Data Symbols

\$PARAMETER is a declaration that precedes the definition of one or more data symbols. In general, each symbol will appear at least once in following ATP data. Data symbols are names (character strings) of arbitrary length that are to be replaced prior to decoding of the data cards as program input. Details about timing of the replacement will follow. The definition of each data symbol occupies one line, and lines are terminated by a blank card as follows:

```
C 34567890
$PARAMETER
< < Indeterminate number of data symbol definitions > >
BLANK card ending data symbol definitions.
```

For illustrations, see standard test cases DC-58, DC-59, DCNEW-19, -25, and -26.

Three types of data symbols exist: 1) Simple character replacement, indicated within apostrophes; 2) mathematical formulas leading to floating point replacement; and 3) mathematical formulas leading to integer serialization of a root character string. Illustrations follow:

- 1) FIVEK = '5.E+3' ---- character string replacement of DCNEW-19;
- 2) _HEIGHT2 = 35. + KNT * 10.0 --- numeric conductor height of DC-59;
- 3) _BUS2_ = KNT + 1. SERIALIZE 'NODE00' --- node name of DC-58.

Simple character replacement (case 1) without mathematics is the easiest to describe. One character string (the name FIVEK on the left) is to be replaced by another of equal length to the right of the equal sign. This is for each occurrence of the name in later data cards. For this illustration, the right hand side is a number (5.E+3), but such is not a requirement. The right hand side could be another character string such as 'CLOSED' for a diode or thyristor (see Section VI-B). One \$PARAMETER definition can be used to control an arbitrary number of following data cards. Switches do not have a reference branch feature the way branches do. But \$PARAMETER can be used to provide such service. Parameters can be defined in one place, and then would copied to many following locations automatically. This is independent of branch type. Wherever a data symbol might be found (including comment cards and in-line comments), it should be replaced.

Mathematical formulas (case 2) are distinguished by lack of apostrophes that enclose the right hand side. Little need be written about the formula because the ATP pocket calculator is used to evaluate the right hand side, and the pocket calculator is described elsewhere (Section I-M). Once a formula has been evaluated, the number is optimally encoded within space equal to that of the symbol name. This includes one leading blank (a property of the optimal encoding). Then substitution proceeds as for the preceding case 1.

Integer serialization (case 3) is identical to case 2 except for the added integer truncation of the result followed by right-adjusted serialization of the root character string that is contained within apostrophes. Rather than floating-point parameters, it is used to encode node names and other character strings within a DO KNT loop as illustrated by a new first subcase of DC-58. Note the characteristic key word SERIALIZE followed by the root character string within apostrophes. There is no special column location for this added information. Of course, the length of the root name within apostrophes should equal the length of the symbol on the left hand side of the equal sign.

The length of a data symbol name must agree with the data field being defined, of course. For example, the inductance field of columns 33-38 of a series R-L-C branch card might be given the 6-character name INDUCT as illustrated in DCNEW-19. That would be for the old, narrow format. But better for most use is the newer, wide format of \$VINTAGE,1, which allows 16 columns of precision. For this, a name such

as MILLIHENRIES might be used as illustrated in DCNEW-19. For long names, it is convenient to add underscore characters as just illustrated. As explained in Section I-M, an underscore character is as good as any letter to indicate the start of a data symbol name. It also can be used freely within the interior of the name, and at the end of the name.

About timing of replacements, the user is offered two choices. If nothing extra is done, data symbol evaluation, and replacement in all following data cards, occur at the time the \$PARAMETER cards are decoded as ATP data. This is the timing of other \$-cards such as \$UNITS: execution is delayed until the card is encountered in natural order as ATP data. Then, the value of each numerical symbol will be confirmed in interpretation. As an illustration, consider Gabor Furst's use to vary resistance as a function of frequency in DCNEW-26. The following evaluation occurred on the first pass, with loop counter KNT = 1:

```
Request precedes analytic symbol definitions. |$PARAMETER { This will be serviced by CIMAGE just as any other $-..
Parameter 1 defined. Value = 2.000000E+00 |RESISTANCE = 2.0 * (1.0 + 0.2 * (KNT - 1.0) ** 1.5) { Funk-Hantel freq. depen
Lack of "=" terminates $PARAMETER definitions. |BLANK card ends $PARAMETER definitions that are processed just b4 branch card
```

START ONLY is the something extra which, when added to \$PARAMETER, will alter the otherwise natural timing of use. \$PARAMETER START ONLY serves to advance usage to the beginning of execution --- before any \$INCLUDE or /-card processing for data sorting by class (see Sections I-J and I-K). After the output of dynamic dimensioning, and before the heading that precedes the first line of data card interpretation, will be found confirmation of the replacement. This is illustrated by DCNEW-19, which involved only one such parameter. This parameter, FIVEK, involved no mathematics:

```
Supplemental offsets. | 240000 742
Next parameter: just simple string replacement. |FIVEK= '5.E+3'
Alternative Transients Program (ATP), Salford 80386 translation. ...
```

Later, when the same data cards are encountered as part of normal data input and interpretation, no action will be taken, although presence of \$PARAMETER START ONLY will be noted. From DCN19.LIS, truncated on the right:

```
Marker card preceding new EMTP data case. |BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
Request precedes analytic symbol definitions. |$PARAMETER START ONLY
Blank card ends $PARAMETER block being ignored. |BLANK card ends $PAR
```

Users of START ONLY are warned about limits of mathematics. Program variables such as DELTAT or KNT have not yet been defined, so their use is meaningless. Simple character replacement (case 1) without mathematics will operate normally, however --- but only in the original data file. Operation will not extend inside any \$INCLUDE file that might be referenced by the original file. This is by design.

POCKET CALCULATOR VARIES PARAMETERS (PCVP) is a request word that commonly is used in conjunction with \$PARAMETER definitions. Yet, PCVP is just one powerful application. It is not a requirement. In fact, \$PARAMETER was developed before PCVP. For details about PCVP, see Section II-A. In the illustration above, variable KNT is the pass number of the PCVP loop. It has values 1, 2, 3, etc., and is the one and only deterministic, independent variable of a PCVP study. Typically network parameters will be made a function of KNT, although randomness is an alternative.

If one symbol is contained within another, the longer must be defined before the shorter. This is illustrated in DCNEW-19. Note that 16-byte MILLIHENRIES precedes 6-byte MILLIH. If the opposite order were attempted (i.e., if MILLIH were defined first), execution would be terminated with an error message as documented on comment cards. Reason for this should be obvious: The longer symbol must not be corrupted by replacement of the shorter one within. This has to do with obvious corruption that would result from original names.

Repeated replacement is a danger about which the user must be warned. The preceding paragraph had to do with original data symbol names. It is only these that are protected. But substitution of the second or later symbol will occur using data that was modified by the first substitution. Rather than original (incoming) data,

of symbols). About number 2, note that symbols can average 15 bytes in length ($300 = 20 * 15$), so it is unlikely this will overflow for numerical use. About number 3, this allows just over 16 occurrences of each of 20 different symbols ($320 = 20 * 16$). Anyway, these are the overflow limits late in November of 1998 as this paragraph is being keyed. No doubt limits will expand with need and time. The initial values are quite arbitrary. On the other hand, since one large block can be segmented into two or more smaller ones (next paragraph), the user can remedy overflow by restructuring of his data.

\$PARAMETER blocks are arbitrary in number, and preceding limits apply to each block individually. Depending on placement in data, two or more might be evaluated at the same point during program execution, or one might be evaluated later than another. It would depend on what other ATP data might separate the two or more \$PARAMETER blocks. Blocks that are not separated by other data always will be evaluated at the same point during program execution, of course. This is true of any and all \$-cards, which continue to be read and processed until exhausted.

I-M. Pocket Calculator

Several ATP features or models require the evaluation of mathematical formulas as could be processed using a scientific pocket calculator. The language of usage is FORTRAN, and all variables and constants are assumed to be double precision floating-point (i.e., 64-bit REAL*8). There is no subscripting, no complex variable, no CALL of a user-supplied subroutine or function, etc., however. This is consistent with free-format supplemental variables of TACS, which have existed since 1982. In fact, faster execution of TACS supplemental variables was the reason for development of the ATP pocket calculator. All library functions available in TACS (see Chapter III) should be available to the user of the pocket calculator, whether or not TACS is involved.

Analytical function evaluation is synonymous with the pocket calculator. This is what the calculator does: evaluate scalar analytical functions one after the other. Either a TACS supplemental variable or a Type-10 electric-network source is defined by an analytical function. To read about introduction of the pocket calculator, look in newsletters for stories about function evaluation. The story title "Analytical Function Evaluation" will be found beginning with the April, 1997, issue.

Compilation is the process of breaking down user-supplied formulas into low-level, machine-language-like instructions that subsequently are executed (perhaps only later, within the time-step loop as would be the case for TACS supplemental variables or Type-10 analytical sources). Thus there are two distinct phases of operation of the pocket calculator: 1) compilation, and 2) execution. An error might occur during either or both. Of course, if the user supplies a formula that somehow is illegal, ATP should reject this during compilation. An example would be mismatched parentheses. On the other hand, both compilation and execution are relatively new, and error checking during compilation is far from exhaustive. So, errors during use must be expected. If operation seems incorrect, first study the analytical expression carefully. If that fails to reveal the cause of the trouble, request DIAGNOSTIC printout, and see if this offers any insight. Compilation always will occur prior to the time-step loop, of course, so will occur in overlays 1 through 15. But remember that \$PARAMETER START ONLY will occur prior to interpretation of the first data card, so the DIAGNOSTIC card is too late. Instead, request diagnostic output using IPRSUP in STARTUP. Search diagnostic output for subroutine names POCKET or MATDAT. If the trouble remains undiagnosed, send an example to Portland for analysis.

Blank characters should be ignored, although they are useful to make formulas more easily readable by humans. As for line length, the limit is the same as for all ATP input lines: 80 bytes. Unlike FORTRAN, columns 73-80 have no special significance (a comment field). Here the model is TACS supplemental variables, which can extend as far as column 80.

Continuation lines are honored by the compiler. Just as in standard FORTRAN 77 (F77), if columns 1-5 are blank and column 6 is non-blank, the present line is taken as a continuation of the preceding one. Yet, whether this is useful in any particular case depends on the type of use. For example, continuation lines are not allowed within \$PARAMETER because code supporting that feature does not honor them. Instead, intermediate variable, indicated by a \$\$, are used. On the other hand, the Type-10 analytically-defined source of the electric network is allowed to have as many continuation cards as the user wants (see the 3rd subcase of DCNEW-19 for a trivial illustration of use).

Numeric constants are recognized during compilation by the presence of a decimal point. This is a special requirement that does not exist in modern FORTRAN: each numeric constant must include a decimal point even if the value is an integer. The only exception is the power of exponentiation as requested by two stars (**). The number following ** is not required to have a decimal point. For example, the 2 of "XX ** 2" is legal. But there could be trouble if any other mathematical operation replaced the two stars. For example, "XX + 2" is not legal, in general. For a power of ten, normal scientific notation should be accepted provided there are no embedded blanks. Either E or D is recognized, and there is no difference between the two. Double precision is used for all storage and computation.

A variable name is distinguished by the absence of a decimal point. See the preceding paragraph for the reason. Also, a variable name must begin with a letter, and is distinguished by lack of any symbol that indicates numeric operation: +, -, *, and /. Yet, this latter requirement is nothing new. It was a requirement of TACS, and a requirement of FORTRAN. The symbols that indicate numerical operation separate variables and constants. Of course, a constant might be signed, but this sign at the start must be separated from what precedes it by either than equal sign or an open parenthesis. This is the standard FORTRAN rule, so should be nothing new. If this is not understood, consult any introductory book about FORTRAN programming.

The underscore character "_" has special meaning for \$PARAMETER symbols. Note use in MILLIHENRIES of DCNEW-19. The underscore character is the one exception to the just-stated general rule that variable names must begin with a letter. For pocket calculator use, the underscore character is considered to be a letter --- a 27th letter to the alphabet. It is the only exception to A through Z for the byte that begins a variable name.

IF statements, statement numbers, and GO TO statements all are allowed for those users who want to make order of execution dependent on data. This is expected to be important when TACS supplemental variables are supported as a replacement for the computationally-inefficient code of Laurent Dube. But support for supplemental variables continue to be delayed as simpler aspects of use are envisioned and developed. Until supplemental variables are made available, if any user might profit from conditional execution of something else, he is invited to write to Portland explaining his idea. Equally important as the compiler capability are assumptions of the code that feed data to the compiler (e.g., code to store and use Type-10 sources). Before IF-related support will be provided, a practical need must be appreciated.

Variable dimensioning of the pocket calculator has not yet been performed. As a result, most tables have fixed sizes, and are capable of overflowing if functions are too numerous or too involved. In theory, there should be protection against overflow, as the following tabulation of overflow errors illustrates:

1) "Overflow limit of 200 on input FORTRAN ..." This refers to a limit on total non-comment lines that are stored at any one time. The issue is complicated since some uses are transitory while others are not. That is, the total number of lines of user-supplied code is not limited to 200. But the number of lines for Type-10 analytical sources is, since all are stored, and later compiled, at the same time.

2) "Ready to overflow limit of 25 on intermediate variables ..." For a discussion of intermediate variables, see \$\$ within the \$PARAMETER instructions of Section I-L. Although intermediate variables are not limited to \$PARAMETER use, this is the dominant initial exploitation.

3) "Ready to overflow limit of 80 on FORTRAN statement ..." This refers to the maximum number of non-blank bytes of each single analytical expression. Initially, the limit is being held to 80. But in fact, the character strings that hold a statement are longer, and it is expected that the limit will expand with time and usage.

4) "Ready to overflow limit of 500 on assembly language" This refers to storage of the compiler output. Since all models that are used in the time-step loop must be stored simultaneously, it is such usage that most commonly will threaten the storage limits of output.

5) "Overflow limit of 20 on parenthesis pairs ..." This limit applies to each FORTRAN statement, of course. It easily could be expanded, if a practical need might ever be demonstrated.